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Towards an Overall Architecture for the NFDI

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Abstract

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) addresses the increasing complexity and fragmentation of research data infrastructures by promoting integration, interoperability, and strategic development across scientific domains. In this context, the Overall Architecture Working Group, established within the NFDI section "Common Infrastructures" [1], is tasked with designing a federated, cross-consortium architecture that enables the sustainable reuse and interconnection of data and services within the NFDI.

Despite significant progress of individual NFDI consortia, current infrastructures remain largely siloed and lack consistent architectural principles for cross-domain collaboration. This paper presents the conceptual basis, objectives, and planned implementation strategy for the development of a coherent overall architecture. Central to the working group's mission is the formulation of a shared vision, a set of guiding technical principles, and a governance model that addresses the diverse needs of the federation of scientific communities while supporting long-term scalability, security, and operational efficiency.

The proposed approach is based on a series of structured activities, including a survey of existing architectural approaches within the NFDI, an analysis of national and international frameworks (like EOSC [2], GAIA-X [3], or ARDC [4]) stakeholder engagement for requirements elicitation, and consolidation of findings into a reusable architectural blueprint. These efforts aim to ensure alignment between consortia, increase adoption through transparent communication, and provide a flexible yet standardised foundation for future developments.

This paper outlines the six key objectives of the working group's concept [5], which, in future, will result in a blueprint and accompanying architectural framework that intended to serve as reference models for current and future NFDI initiatives: (1) developing a common vision for a federated infrastructure, (2) defining the strategic contributions of NFDI consortia, (3) leveraging existing services for sustainable implementation, (4) conducting a stakeholder-driven requirements analysis, (5) identifying infrastructure dynamics across consortia, and (6) proposing a transparent and adaptable governance structure.

By detailing the work plan and corresponding milestones - from the collection of architectural best practices to the delivery of a comprehensive technical framework - this paper demonstrates how a coordinated architectural effort can support interoperability, enable collaborative development, and foster national and international research data collaborations. The paper

also outlines initial collaborations with various NFDI consortia and explores potential synergies with global infrastructure initiatives.

This paper contributes to the discourse on federated research infrastructures and provides a strategic reference point for the design of integrative, community-driven architectures within the NFDI and beyond by presenting the conceptual framework and planned activities of the Overall Architecture Working Group.

Keywords: NFDI, Architecture, Federated Infrastructure

Resources

Not Applicable.

Author contributions

Marius Politze: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft; **Philipp Wieder:** Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft; **Sonja Schimmler:** Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft; **Michael Diepenbroek:** Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft

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